

Diabetic Retinopathy Detection using ResNet-18 Architecture

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Abstract—Diabetic retinopathy is a time-consuming diagnosis of a consequence of diabetes mellitus that affects the retina. It needs skilled clinicians to recognize subtle characteristics in colored fundus images. The study suggests using CNN to detect diabetic retinopathy in fundus photos. The data is prepared using a unique segmentation approach that makes use of Gabor filters, and the small dataset size is addressed through data augmentation. To train the model, ResNet18 algorithm has been used with the help of a powerful Graphics Processing Unit (GPU). The suggested approach shows encouraging outcomes in the identification of diabetic retinopathy, suggesting its potential for use in clinical settings. Its efficacy is demonstrated by the 71.51 percent accuracy on the training dataset.

Keywords—Convolutional Neural Networks(CNN), ResNet18, Image Classification, Fundus Image, Diabetic Retinopathy, Retinal Disease

I. INTRODUCTION

Diabetic retinopathy, a common complication of diabetes mellitus, poses a significant threat to vision worldwide, affecting approximately 80% of diabetics who have had the disease for over two decades. Early diagnosis and timely intervention can prevent up to 90% of vision loss cases associated with diabetic retinopathy. However, the conventional approach to detecting diabetic retinopathy relies heavily on manual examination of fundus images by skilled specialists, making it time-consuming and prone to human error.

A novel method that combines a multitasking model with Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) has been used to diagnose diabetic retinopathy in order to overcome these difficulties. CNNs have shown promise in a range of image analysis tasks by lowering the requirement for considerable preprocessing due to their capacity to directly examine images at the pixel level. By using deep learning algorithms to produce accurate and efficient forecasts, the objective is to eliminate the human factor from the diagnosing process.

One of the primary challenges with training deep neural networks is the degradation problem, which occurs when the network's depth increases and leads to a saturation and ensuing drop in accuracy. To tackle this challenge, a Deep

Residual Learning method that takes cues from the ResNet18 architecture has been applied. ResNet18, a strong powerful deep learning network, has proven to perform better in image recognition tests. Using residual connections helps prevent the vanishing gradient issue when training very deep networks (up to 18 layers).

This should increase the precision and dependability of the diagnosis method by utilizing the robustness and efficiency of the ResNet18 model in the diabetic retinopathy detection system. The ResNet18 architecture is well suited because of its ability to extract precise information from the fundus images, along with its high-level abstraction capabilities. Using the exclusive dataset, its task-specific flexibility and performance can be further enhanced by adjusting its ore-trained weights.

The paper proposes a CNN-based model that combines deep learning skills with transfer learning techniques to identify Diabetic Retinopathy. By using large-scale datasets and pre-trained models like ResNet18 to optimize the diagnosis of diabetic retinopathy, the aim is to improve patient outcomes and reduce the workload of healthcare professionals.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Kaiming et. al.[1] refers about how Residual learning frameworks have revolutionized deep neural network training by enabling greater depth while maintaining accuracy. These frameworks restructure network layers to learn residual functions based on input references, rather than standalone functions. Empirical evidence, including evaluations on ImageNet with up to 152 layers, demonstrates their effectiveness in achieving state-of-the-art performance in various visual recognition tasks.

Manasi et. al.[2] highlights the development of a CNN-based method for detecting diabetic retinopathy (DR) in fundus images. The study emphasizes the importance of automated systems due to the time-consuming nature of manual diagnosis. By leveraging Gabor filters for segmentation and ResNet50 for training, the proposed method shows promising results, achieving an accuracy of 71.51 percent.

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M. A. K. Raiaan et. al. [3] presents RetNet-10, a shallow convolutional neural network (CNN) for five different DR class classification of fundus images. Through the combination of three different datasets and a range of preprocessing and augmentation methods, RetNet-10 surpasses previous state-of-the-art models with a testing accuracy of 98.65%.

Allena et. al.[4] focuses on enhancing the performance of the RESNET18 model, a widely used architecture in deep learning, by adding a sequential layer for image classification tasks. It utilizes the Adam optimizer and the Negative Log Likelihood (NLL) loss function, which is particularly effective for unbalanced training sets. The results demonstrate improved accuracy when using the RESNET18 architecture with an additional sequential layer, consisting of linear, dropout, and ReLU activation functions followed by LogSoftmax.

Sharma et. al.[5] conducted an empirical analysis of the performance of popular convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for real-time object identification in video feeds. The study focuses on three widely used CNN architectures: AlexNet, GoogLeNet, and ResNet50, and evaluates their performance on three benchmark datasets: ImageNet, CIFAR10, and CIFAR100. Unlike traditional approaches that rely solely on single datasets for evaluation, this study utilizes multiple datasets to assess the networks' capabilities comprehensively.

Q.Qiao et. al.[6] explores the integration of machine learning into image processing, investigating various image processing technologies through the lens of machine learning. It provides a comprehensive overview of popular image processing techniques, comparing and highlighting the limitations of each method. Additionally, the paper introduces machine learning algorithms, particularly convolutional neural networks (CNNs), for feature extraction in image processing.

III. METHODOLOGY

The methodology employed in this research leverages a combination of data preprocessing, model development, and evaluation techniques to address the task of diabetic retinopathy severity classification. Initially, a comprehensive dataset of retinal images is collected and preprocessed, ensuring standardization and optimal compatibility for subsequent analysis. Following exploratory data analysis to understand the dataset's characteristics, transfer learning with the ResNet-18 architecture is adopted for model development.

Data augmentation strategies are employed to enhance model robustness and generalization. Training is conducted with carefully chosen hyperparameters, including loss functions and optimizers. The resulting model is rigorously evaluated, considering various performance metrics and techniques to validate its efficacy in diabetic retinopathy severity classification.

A. Data Collection and Preprocessing

The dataset used in this research consists of retinal images sourced from Kaggle, which are essential for diagnosing diabetic retinopathy (DR). These images are crucial for identifying the severity of DR, which can range from no DR to proliferative DR.

The preprocessing steps are vital to ensure consistency and readiness for model training. Initially, the images are accessed from their respective class folders using Python libraries such as OpenCV and NumPy. This step involves loading the images into memory for further processing.

Subsequently, to standardize the images for uniformity, they are resized to a predefined size, commonly set to 128x128 pixels. This resizing step is crucial for ensuring that all images are of the same dimensions, allowing for consistent processing across the dataset.

Figure 1: Moderate DR

Additionally, to facilitate effective model training, the pixel values of the images are normalized to fall within the range of [0, 1]. Normalization is essential for enhancing model convergence during training, as it helps prevent issues such as vanishing or exploding gradients. By standardizing the images through resizing and normalization, the dataset is prepared for subsequent steps such as model training and evaluation.

B. Exploratory Data Analysis

Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) begins with visual exploration of the dataset, aimed at gaining insights into the distribution of classes and characteristics of images. Sample images from each class are displayed using matplotlib, pyplot allowing the assessment of image diversity and identify potential class imbalances. The objective of this is to understand the dataset's composition, detect any anomalies or artifacts, and inform subsequent steps in model development and evaluation. Through visual inspection of sample images, valuable insights are gained from the dataset's characteristics, such as variations in image quality, presence of artifacts, and distribution of classes.


```

# Training Loop
for epoch in range(num_epochs):
    # Set the model to training mode
    resnet18.train()

    running_loss = 0.0
    correct_predictions = 0
    total_samples = 0

    for inputs, labels in train_loader:
        inputs, labels = inputs.float().to(device), labels.to(device)

        # Zero the gradients
        optimizer_instance.zero_grad()
        # Forward pass
        outputs = resnet18(inputs)

        # Compute loss
        loss = criterion(outputs, labels)

        # Backward pass
        loss.backward()

        # Update weights
        optimizer_instance.step()

        # Update statistics
        running_loss += loss.item() * inputs.size(0)
        _, predicted = torch.max(outputs, 1)
        correct_predictions += (predicted == labels).sum().item()
        total_samples += labels.size(0)

```

Fig 4 : Model Training using ResNet-18

IV. RESULT

The research investigates the application of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for automating the detection of diabetic retinopathy in fundus photos, addressing the challenge of time-consuming manual diagnosis by skilled clinicians. Leveraging a unique segmentation approach utilizing Gabor filters and mitigating the limitations of a small dataset through data augmentation, the study employs the ResNet18 algorithm trained on a powerful Graphics Processing Unit (GPU).

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The proposed methodology demonstrates promising outcomes, achieving a notable 71.51% accuracy on the training dataset. These results underscore the potential of deep learning techniques in facilitating accurate and efficient diabetic retinopathy diagnosis, suggesting practical implications for clinical settings.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the research endeavors to streamline the diagnosis of diabetic retinopathy through the utilization of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and advanced image processing techniques. By harnessing the power of deep learning algorithms such as ResNet18 and employing innovative segmentation methods, the study demonstrates promising results in automating the detection of diabetic retinopathy from fundus photos. The success achieved in this study underscores the potential of artificial intelligence in augmenting clinical practices, offering faster and more accurate diagnoses while alleviating the burden on healthcare professionals.

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